

Potentiometric Studies on Stepwise Mixed Ligand Chelate Formation of La(III), Pr(III) or Nd(III)-N-Hydroxy Ethylethylenediamine-N, N', N',-Triacetic Acid-Mercapto Acids

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Stoution equilibrium studies on the interaction between 1 : 1, Ln(III)-HEDTA binary chelate (where Ln(III) = La(III), Pr(III) or Nd(III); HEDTA = N-hydroxyethyl-ethylenediamine-N, N', N'-triacetic acid) with certain mercapto acids such as thioglycollic (TGA) and thiomalic (TMEA) have been carried out potentiometrically. Formation constants of the resulting mixed ligand chelates, MAL (where M = La(III), Pr(III) or Nd(III); A = HEDTA and L = TGA or TMEA) have been determined at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ and $\mu = 0.1$ (KNO₃). The values of the formation constant K_{MAL} have been interpreted in terms of electrostatic repulsion indicating that the contribution due to π -interaction in M-S bond is not significant. The order of stability in terms of metal ions has been found to be La(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III) and in terms of secondary ligand as TGA < TMEA.

N-hydroxyethylethylenediamine-N, N', N'-triacetic acid is known to form quite stable complexes with a number of metal ions¹⁻³ and behaves as a pentadentate ligand⁴. In case the coordination number of the metal ion is not satisfied during the formation of binary complex (MA), the remaining sites are occupied by the water molecules or hydroxide ions^{5,6}. However, in presence of a bidentate ligand these may be replaced resulting in the mixed ligand chelate (MAL) formation. Mercapto acids are known to interact with metal ions at higher pH⁷⁻¹¹ and the systems are interesting due to the presence of M-S bond¹². In the present communication an attempt has been made to investigate the systems MAL, where M = La(III), Pr(III) or Nd(III); A = HEDTA and L = TGA or TMEA, in order to observe the contributions of π interaction in the M-S bond.

Experimental

The rare-earth oxides were of spectral grade and a stock solution was prepared and standardised as described in earlier communication¹³. The dipotassium salt of HEDTA (Koch Light, England) was prepared by dissolving its known amount in the required volume of KOH (0.1 M). The solutions of thioglycollic (E. Merck) and thiomalic (E. Merck) acids were prepared by direct weighing and standardized potentiometrically. All the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and the following pH-metric titrations were carried out at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ using a Cambridge pH-meter standardized against 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate solution.

1. 10ml (0.025 M) mercapto acid.
2. 10ml (0.025 M) dipotassium salt of HEDTA in presence of 10ml (0.025 M) Ln-nitrate (Ln(III)-HEDTA, 1 : 1).
3. 10ml (0.025 M) dipotassium salt of HEDTA in presence of 10ml (0.025 M) Ln-nitrate and 10ml (0.025 M) mercapto acid (Ln(III)-HEDTA-Mercapto acid, 1 : 1 : 1).

The ionic strength of all the solutions was kept constant ($\mu = 0.1$) by adding 5ml. of 1M potassium nitrate and the total volume was raised to 50 ml in each case. The titrations were carried out in presence of an inert atmosphere.

Results and Discussion

Curves a and a' (Figs.1 to 3) represent the potentiometric titrations of thioglycollic and thiomalic acids respectively. The acid dissociation constants (k_1 , k_2 or k_3) of these ligands were calculated by algebraic method described by Chaberek and Martell¹⁴. The values of pk_1 and pk_2 in case of thiomalic acid were taken from the literature¹⁵ and presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AT $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Ligand	pk_1	pk_2	pk_3
Thioglycollic acid	3.61	10.23	
Thiomalic acid	3.64	4.64	10.32

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TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES

L	$\mu=0.1;$		$t=30\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	
	$\text{Log } K_{\text{La.HEDTA}}^{\text{La.HEDTA.L}}$		$\text{Log } K_{\text{Pr.HEDTA}}^{\text{Pr.HEDTA.L}}$	$\text{Log } K_{\text{Nd.HEDTA}}^{\text{Nd.HEDTA.L}}$
TGA	3.18 ± 0.08		3.55 ± 0.09	3.77 ± 0.08
TMEA	3.67 ± 0.05		3.94 ± 0.06	4.22 ± 0.07

Curve b, (Figs. 1 to 3) may be attributed to the titration of 1 : 1 binary mixtures of Ln(III)-HEDTA, which exhibits an inflexion at $m=1$ (m =moles of base added per mole of metal ion). The inflexion at $m=1$, may be correlated to the formation of 1 : 1 M(III)-HEDTA binary chelates due to the neutralization of the free proton of the carboxylic group of HEDTA. The superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve¹⁶ in the lower buffer region supports the stepwise formation of the mixed ligand chelates in each case and the interaction of thio acid starts just after the complete formation of 1 : 1, M(III)-HEDTA binary complex. The initial lowering of pH

Fig. 1. Potentiometric Titrations of La(III)-HEDTA-TGA; TMEA Ternary systems, (a) TGA; (a') TMEA; (b) 1:1, La(III)-HEDTA; (d) 1:1:1 La(III)-HEDTA-TGA; (d') 1:1:1 La(III)-HEDTA-TMEA; (c, c') corresponding composite curves of mixed systems. m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion.

in the case of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary systems (curves d and d', Figs. 1 to 3) may be due to the ionization of the proton of the carboxylic groups of mercapto acids. The formation constants K_{MAL} of the resulting mixed ligand chelates have been calculated (1) and listed in Table 2.

Fig. 2. Potentiometric Titrations of Pr(III)-HEDTA-TGA; TMEA Ternary systems. (a) TGA; (a') TMEA; (b) 1:1, Pr(III)-HEDTA; (d) 1:1:1 Pr(III)-HEDTA-TGA; (d') 1:1:1 Pr(III)-HEDTA-TMEA; (c, c') corresponding composite curves of mixed systems. m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion.

Systems : Ln(III)-HEDTA-TGA

Curve d (Figs. 1 to 3) corresponds to the potentiometric titration of 1 : 1 : 1 Ln(III)-HEDTA-TGA ternary systems and a sharp inflexion at $m=2$, may be correlated to the neutralization of the carboxylic proton in mercapto acid prior to its interaction with the 1 : 1, Ln(III)-HEDTA simple chelate. After $m=2$, a lower buffer region starts clearly showing the formation of the mixed ligand chelate (MAL) between $m=2$ to $m=3$ and this can be further substantiated by comparing the curve d (Figs. 1 to 3) with the corresponding composite curve c.

Systems : Ln(III)-HEDTA-TMEA

The equimolar systems, Ln(III)-HEDTA-TMEA (curve d', Figs. 1 to 3) on titration give a sharp inflexion at $m=3$, which indicates that the neutralization of the carboxylic protons in the thiomalic acid takes place prior to its interaction with 1 : 1, Ln(III)-HEDTA binary complex. The lowering of the buffer region after $m=3$ indicates the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed species. The existence of such species between $m=3$ to 4 may be further substantiated by comparing the curve d' (Figs. 1 to 3) with the corresponding composite curve c'.

Fig. 3. Potentiometric Titrations of Nd(III)-HEDTA- TGA, TMEA ternary systems-(a)TGA ; (a') TMEA ; (b) 1:1, Nd(III)-HEDTA ; (d) 1:1:1 Nd(III)-HEDTA-TGA, (d') 1:1:1 Nd(III)-HEDTA-TMETA ; (c, c') corresponding composite curves of mixed systems m =moles of base added per mole of metalion.

It may however, be noted that the value of K_{MAL}^{MA} increases from La(III) to Nd(III) and this trend can reasonably be explained¹⁷ on the basis of the increasing complexing power of the rare earth ions as the atomic number increases.

The value of K_{MAL} has been found to be lower than K_{MA}^4 in each case. It may be due to the absence of electrostatic attraction between the incoming charged hydroxy acid ion and the neutral 1 : 1, Ln(III)-HEDTA simple chelate, basicity of the incoming ligand and steric interference of HEDTA which occupies more space around the metal ion.

The stability of $K_{M.HEDTA}^{M.HEDTA.L}$ (where L =Glycolic

(GA) or malic acid (MEA) has been reported¹⁸ and found to be greater than $K_{M.HEDTA.L}^{M.HEDTA}$ (where L =TGA or TMEA). This may be explained on the basis of the fact that rare-earth ion behaves as a class 'A' acceptor for which oxygen is a better donor atom. It is, therefore, concluded that M- π -interaction, even if present, has no significant contribution to the stability in these cases.

In terms of the secondary ligands the formation constants of the resulting biligand complexes of any particular rare-earth ion increase in the following order:

The greater stability of the thiomalic acid complexes may be due to the increase in the number of chelate rings formed and the basicity of the ligand involved.

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